

FEATURES OF PRIMARY DISABILITY IN PERSONS DIFFERENT AGES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN)

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Annotation. The paper presents an analysis of the primary disability of people of working and retirement age. Studied gender characteristics, causes, severity of disability in people of different ages.

Key words: primary disability, age structure of disability, gender characteristics of disability, causes of disability.

The deterioration of medical, social and sanitary and hygienic indicators of the health of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan is associated with an increase in chronic socially significant diseases that lead to permanent disability. At present, in Uzbekistan, as in most countries of the world community, the redistribution of the demographic burden in favor of an older city continues. Violation of the functional functions of the body against the background of polymorbidity against the background of the elderly, in combination with the environment, the main types of life activity lead to psychological maladaptation and social disintegration. The incidence rate in the elderly is 2.4 times, and in old age - 6 times higher in comparison with the incidence rate in middle-aged people. More than 70% of older people have five or six chronic diseases and need medical and social assistance, which leads to an increase in disability both in the country as a whole and in the region.

Purpose of the work: analysis of the age, gender structure of primary disability and its causes.

Materials and methods: the analysis of outpatient cards of elderly and senile people, recognized as disabled for the first time, was carried out. The polymorbidity index was calculated (Lazebnik L.B., 2000). The level of independent activity was selectively determined (Katz, 1989). In the work, survey maps of older people were used.

Results of the study: among 349 people who were initially referred for examination at the Bureau of Medical and Social Expertise and recognized as disabled - 171 (49.0%) people were of working age (men - 109, women - 62), 178 (51.0%) - of working age (54 men, 124 women). Of these, 120 (34.4%) were elderly (39 men, 81 women) and 58 were elderly (16.6%): 15 men, 43 women.

their characteristic features. The lowest rate of primary disability was observed in young people (up to 44 years old) - 32 people. In the structure of primary disability of people of working age, men prevailed in a ratio of 2:1. Among elderly and senile persons, women prevailed among persons with disabilities, 2:1 and 3:1, respectively, probably due to the fact that fewer men than women survive to this age. Analysis of data on the severity of disability showed that group III disability was predominantly established in young people (in 76% of cases), middle-aged people (in 69% of cases) and in 54.2% of elderly patients. Only 17.3% of people of senile age were recognized as disabled of group III. There was a predominance of high degree disability (groups I and II) in persons over 75 years of age (82.7% of cases). When determining groups I and II of disability, the most socially significant were significantly pronounced limitations or impossibility of habitual life activity. The severity index of primary disability among geronts was 68.7 ñ per 10,000 population. In the structure of primary disability in people of working age, the leading place was occupied by diseases of the circulatory system - 33.5%, diseases of the musculoskeletal system, including post-traumatic injuries, accounted for 26.3%, malignant neoplasms - 19.3%, other diseases - 20 ,nine%. Among the causes of disability in the elderly, the first ranking place was occupied by diseases of the circulatory system (37.0%), among which IHD dominated (post-infarction atherosclerosis, stable angina III-IV FC, cardiac arrhythmias complicated by heart failure), arterial hypertension and cerebrovascular diseases. Malignant neoplasms occupied the second ranking place (31.4%). In men, cancer of the gastrointestinal tract, lungs and oropharynx, kidneys and urinary tract more often led to disability. In women, cancer of the breast, female genital organs, and intestines was more common. Diseases of the musculoskeletal system and involutive changes in the musculoskeletal system caused persistent functional disorders in 10.2% of patients. The fourth ranking among the causes of disability in older people was occupied by diseases of the organ of vision (5.0%), other diseases among the causes of disability accounted for 16.4%. In the structure of the pathology of elderly people, which led to disability, the leading place belonged to cerebrovascular pathology (strokes, chronic cerebral ischemia) - 41.0%, malignant neoplasms - 27.3%, diseases of the heart and blood vessels - 11.0%, involutive changes in the musculoskeletal system. motor apparatus, post-traumatic injuries - 11.4%, diseases of the organ of vision, hearing - 7.0%, other diseases - 2.3%. An inversely proportional relationship between age and polymorbidity was revealed. The polymorbidity index in the elderly was 5.43 ± 0.7 diseases/one patient, and in the group of elderly people it was 3.06 ± 0.4

diseases/one patient. To judge the limitation of capacity, the level of self-service, differentiation of the degree of care in 76 patients, the value of the index of independent activity was determined. Daily activity index equal to 3-6 points was found in 12.3% of men and 21.2% of women, 7-13 points - in 23.1% of men and 27.4% of women; 14 points for men - 6.8%, women - 9.2%. Consequently, the majority of men (35.4%) and women (48.6%) needed occasional or permanent care.

Conclusions: among those recognized as disabled for the first time, persons of working age predominated. In the gender structure of primary disability in patients of working age, men were in the lead, among persons with disabilities of elderly and senile age, women predominated. Disability group III dominated among young, middle-aged and elderly people, groups I and II dominated among people over 75 years of age.

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